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USE OF METHODS AND APPROACHES TO FORM THE COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE OF SCHOOL STUDENTS IN ENGLISH LESSONS

Kulmagambetova S.,

*candidate of pedagogic sciences, associate professor
M. Utemisov West Kazakhstan university*

Gatauova A.

master student

M. Utemisov West Kazakhstan university

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Abstract

The main aim of using methods and approaches in English lessons is to develop students' communicative competence. This means developing their communication skills, communicative competence and culture. That is why the English teacher should actively use appropriate methods and approaches in lessons to impart knowledge, skills and abilities in order to realize the learners' learning achievements. The global community's desire for common educational programmes and standards is dictated by the technological, economic and political transformations that are unfolding in major countries around the world today. The problem of creating a common European educational space has highlighted the problem of improving the quality of teaching English as a language of international communication. The fact of Kazakhstan's accession to the Council of Europe has determined the necessity of harmonising Kazakhstan educational standards with the common European standards. The materials of the Council of Europe address two types of foreign language competence: general competence and communicative language competence.

Keywords: method, approach, formation, communicative competence, education, intensive, implementation, interaction.

The world is changing, it getting smaller and smaller and changing into a global village in terms of very near, intensive interrelations and interactions of countries. All countries' borders are open so the interaction of nations has become so close and intensive as never before. And people are changing and consequence of these alterations we can observe in every field of life, in education, culture, economy, language, policy and so on [1 pp.14]. Approximately 20-30 years from now there were definite standards to education, learners had to maintain knowledge, skills and learners' outputs, nowadays these standards are unfashionable, instead, learners should maintain communicative competence in order to be competent and competitive school students.

In the teaching of foreign language, a great attention is given to the sequence of learning processes. The listen-speak-read-write is widely conducted for all levels, while the type of transition between these skills and the length of time spent on each one are defined by the needs of each group of students. In the classroom procedure the teacher as well the students should speak only target language which in its turn should be trained by a native speaker. However, in most state schools there aren't native speakers, thus local teachers take a role of a native speaker. A variety of methods are used. The students learn the language in a gradual manner, pattern by pattern, in a way similar to that in which a student learn his first language, with minimum of grammatical analysis. A method means a way to achieve a goal. In modern foreign language teaching methods is interpreted in a broad and narrow sense. In a broad

sense method means a system of teaching. In a narrow sense, method means a way of orderly activity of the teacher and the learner on the way to achieving the set learning objectives. Thus, method is, in fact, a way of enabling interaction a students and a teacher.

In order to ensure effective learning activities for learners the teacher uses a variety of methods, they might vary depending on the objective of the lesson and which of four skills (reading, writing, listening, speaking) the teacher aims to develop. There are four distinct methods of teaching reading, which have developed about 30 years from now. These methods are: the all-oral methods, the all-silent method, the silent-oral method, combining the methods. Most teachers might use all of these methods at different times, combining them in their efforts to do whatever what is the best for their children [2, p.75-76].

While teaching a foreign language the use methods and approaches often isn't enough, so it would be preferable to include illustration (video, slides, pictures), explanation and exercises. According to Konyshva A.B. nowadays a lot of teachers use in their teaching functional-thinking tables. They are diagrams and a work system with diagrams are made for individual communicative possession of lexical units. The use of aforementioned diagrams gives a teacher the possibility to present new lexical units in a good manner, and in its turn, these tables encourage students to use new words in their speech. It should be noted that methods are universal in nature and are used in any methodological system. The use of the communicative

approach means to be predominant of communicative exercises [3, p. 69].

The foreign language learning process includes three main methodological stages:

- the stage of presentation of new material;
- training stage;

-the stage of application of the learnt material in the process of communication in different types of speech activity. At each stage, appropriate methods are used.

In the presentation stage the teacher demonstrates of new material and how to use it. The teacher demonstrates samples of speech and shows how they function in context. This demonstration can be carried out with the help of a picture, an object, action and so on. In the practice phase the teacher offers the learners exercises which are based on the application of the learnt material in oral or written communication.

It should be noted that learning activities are managed by the teacher's control of school students' progress in acquiring foreign language speech activities at each stage of learning. For their part, students use self-monitoring and self-assessment.

In order to develop communicative, informative, sociocultural competence through language lessons the teacher should use types of methods, paradigms, approaches. According to Findley and Nathan (1980) competency-based education refers to "a philosophical system or model in an educational service where "competency is the specification of a capability in designated areas of knowledge, assessed through student performance" [4 p.25]. Competency-based education emerged in the United States in the 1970s and refers to an educational movement. A big number of famous and competent scholars such as Richards, J and Rodgers, T. (2001), Savage, L. (1993), Schneck, and E.A. (1978) stated their valuable ideas and thoughts in this field. According to Richards, J and Rodgers (2001) competency-based education advocates "defining educational goals in terms of precise measurable description of knowledge, skills and behavior" [5, p.22]. We suppose the outcomes of learning is essential for the learners in the future lives and cannot be ignored.

Social expectations, connected with education of competency, carry higher indicators of quality of learning owing to level of individualization, interaction with environment, of educational routes. Thus teaching basic competency represents itself as a priority mission which is at the stage of formation of multilevel secondary education. Its formation should not go necessarily under the uniform scheme, assuming a freedom in

choosing, development of individuality and competence of learners.

Every stage of learning (primary, secondary and high school) isn't characterized only by of topics and scope of the material for communication training however diversified forms, methods of study according to the curriculum of the educational establishment. In this context each stage should have its own aims and objective. Implementing a communicative approach in the learning process in English language teaching means that the formation of the communicative competence of learners takes place through their implementation of English-language speech activities. In other words, the acquisition of the means of communication (phonetic, lexical, grammatical) is aimed at their practical application in the process of communication. Speaking, listening, reading and writing skills are acquired through the implementation of these types of speech activities in the learning process under conditions that simulate real communication situations. Thus, learning activities are organized in such a way that they perform motivated actions with the language material in order to achieve communicative objectives and intentions of communication [6, pp.220]. English language learning in secondary school takes place in different spheres of intellectual and everyday communication: social and domestic, socio-political and socio-cultural.

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